

INVESTIGATION OF POTENTIAL STRESS PARAMETERS IN RAINBOW TROUT (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*)

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The transportation of rainbow trout in the presence of the anesthetic clove oil was investigated. Before the transportation tests, an acute experiment was conducted to verify that removal of the fish from the water for one minute does not significantly increase the glucose or cortisol concentration of the blood plasma. In the main experiment two different transportation conditions were compared: transport in water only and in water with anesthetic. During transportation without addition of clove oil, blood plasma glucose and cortisol concentrations changed significantly. The concentration of glucose increased from 4.92 mmol/L prior to transportation to 6.16 mmol/L and values similar to the initial ones (4.95 mmol/L) were observed 5 hours after transportation. Concentration of the stress hormone cortisol increased from the initial 37.2 ng/mL to 89.2 ng/mL and returned to a value of 36.1 ng/mL 3 hours post transportation. Respective values of glucose concentration have not changed significantly during transportation in the presence of clove oil (4.3; 4.4; 4.4 mmol/L), whereas those of cortisol showed a slight decrease with the passing of time (28.1; 26.7; 20.18 ng/mL). Results show that transportation stress can significantly be reduced by the use of anesthetics.